

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Article

Study On Efficacy and Compliance of Oral Supplements with Ferric Pyrophosphate and Ferrous Ascorbate in Iron Deficiency Anaemia During Pregnancy

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ARTICLE INFO

Published: 07 May 2025

Keywords:

Ferric ascorbate, Ferric pyrophosphate, Iron deficiency anaemia, Iron supplementation, Maternal morbidity, Pregnancy, Preterm birth, Postpartum haemorrhage.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.15354355

ABSTRACT

Background: Iron deficiency anaemia in pregnancy is a nutritional disorder characterized by insufficient iron levels, leading to reduced haemoglobin production. This condition poses significant risks to both maternal and fetal health including increased chances of preterm birth, low birth, weight and maternal morbidity. It often results from inadequate dietary intake, poor iron absorption, or increased iron requirements during pregnancy. Early diagnosis and appropriate management through iron supplementation and dietary adjustments are crucial to mitigate adverse outcomes and promote healthy pregnancy outcomes. **Objective:** To evaluate the efficacy and compliance with oral ferric pyrophosphate and oral ferrous ascorbate **Method:** A prospective observational study for a duration of 3 months with 83 subjects divided into 2 groups Group-A with 43 subjects receiving Ferric ascorbate and Group-B with 40 subjects receiving with ferric pyrophosphate. Both the groups received a dose of 100mg oral tablets. **Result:** Ferrous Ascorbate showed an increase of Hb levels from 9.52 g/dL to 12.23 g/dL Serum Ferritin increased from 74.56ng/mL to 288.23ng/mL whereas in Ferric Pyrophosphate the Hb levels resulted from 9.82g/dL to 11.16g/dL and Serum Ferritin values increased from 82.63ng/mL to 314.18ng/mL. **Conclusion:** Efficacy of Ferrous Ascorbate group was found to be better, but the Ferric Pyrophosphate group had better compliance compared to Ferrous Ascorbate.

INTRODUCTION

Anaemia is defined by the World Health Organization (WHO) as haemoglobin (Hb) levels

of less than 11 g/dL for pregnant women and 12 g/dL for nonpregnant adults ^(1,2). From 2015 to 2016, more than half of Indian women aged 15 to 49 were anaemic.

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Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

The Ministry of Health and Family Welfare of India conducted National Family Health Surveys (NFHS) in 2005-2006 and 2015-2016, which revealed a high prevalence of anaemia among women^(3,4). Iron Deficiency Anaemia (IDA) during pregnancy is the condition that can have detrimental effects on the health and well-being of both the expectant mother and her developing fetus. Preterm delivery, low birth weight, intrauterine development retardation, postpartum haemorrhage, heart failure, and an elevated risk of infections are among the consequences⁽⁵⁾. For the treatment of mild to moderate IDA, oral iron supplementation is employed, but parenteral therapy is required for severe cases. For patients who are malabsorption or have an intolerance to oral iron preparations, parenteral preparations are also the recommended option. Iron supplementation by oral formulations is both efficient and well-tolerated. To reach the desired Hb levels, iron supplementation should be continued for at least two months, depending on the specific patient. For optimal therapy compliance, an iron preparation with a favorable tolerability is therefore necessary. Iron deficiency anemia is most usually treated with ferrous forms of ascorbate, sulphate, fumarate, gluconate, glutamate, succinate, and lactate, as well as ferric forms such as ferric pyrophosphate and ferric orthophosphate iron supplements. The physiological form of iron that the intestines absorb is when it is in the ferrous state. In the alkaline pH of the small intestine, iron in the ferric form is transformed into insoluble ferric hydroxide, which has reduced absorption (iron from supplements containing ferric forms must be converted into ferrous forms for absorption following oral therapy)⁽⁶⁾. The advantage of ferrous ascorbate over other ferrous salts in iron

supplements is that it is known to stay soluble in the small intestine's alkaline pH⁽⁷⁾. However, the gastrointestinal mucosa is toxic to oral iron supplements, which are typically in the form of ferrous (Fe²⁺) salts, and intolerance is widespread, leading to poor patient compliance and treatment failure⁽⁸⁾. Given that ferrous ascorbic causes metallic taste in the mouth and results in black or tarry stools, doctors typically prescribe ferric pyrophosphate instead of ferrous ascorbate⁽⁹⁾. Hence, the goal of the current study was to evaluate the effectiveness, tolerability, compliance, and adverse effects of the prescribed Ferric pyrophosphate over Ferrous ascorbic for the treatment of IDA in expectant mothers.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study setting and design:

This is a prospective observational study which was conducted for about 3 months duration after the approval of the Institutional Ethics Committee at Durgabai Deshmukh Hospital and Research Centre – Hyderabad, India. After providing the complete details about this study to the patients, they were given Informed consent and Patient consent forms and upon their willingness to participate in the study, we have recruited the subjects.

Study criteria:

Inclusion Criteria:

According to the WHO guidelines for IDA, Pregnant women of gestational age between 12 to 26 weeks with moderate anaemia. Having blood haemoglobin levels between 7 and 9.9 g/dl shown in (Fig. 1).

Population	Non-Anemia*	Mild Anemia*	Moderate Anemia*	Severe Anemia*
6-59 months of age	≥ 11	10-10.9	7-9.9	<7
5-11 years of age	≥ 11.5	11-11.4	8-10.9	<8
12-14 years of age	≥ 12	11-11.9	8-10.9	<8
Non-pregnant women (≥ 15 years)	≥ 12	11-11.9	8-10.9	<8
Pregnant women	≥11	10-10.9	7-9.9	<7
Men (≥ 15 years)	≥13	11-12.9	8-10.9	<8

Fig 1: WHO classification of anemia according to age and severity

Exclusion Criteria:

- subjects with Haemoglobinopathy and bleeding by pregnancy complication,
- severe concurrent illness (cardiovascular, renal, hepatic or any other systemic diseases);
- history of hypersensitivity to iron preparations were excluded from the study.
- patients with active internal bleeding.

Sampling strategy and size:

We recruited 98 subjects based on their interest to participate. Patients were randomly allocated into two groups –Group-A: **Ferrous Ascorbate** group and Group-B: **Ferric Pyrophosphate** group, each group consisting of equal number of participants ie) 49 in each group.

Ferric pyrophosphate:

Trade name: Ferrinto

Chemical formula^[10]: $Fe_4 (P_2 O_7)^3$

Manufacturer, city and the country: Swiss gamier biotech Pvt.Ltd, Himachal Pradesh, India.

Ferric ascorbate:

Trade name: Orofer XT.

Chemical formula^[11]: $C_{12}H_{14}FeO_{12}$.

Manufacturer, city and the country: Emcure pharmaceuticals LTD, Bari- brahmana, Jammu, India.

Study procedure:

Prior to the starting of the study patient counselling was given to all the participants about the medication and the importance of diet guidelines and told them to call the Principal Investigator anytime regarding any queries related to medicines. Group-A received 100mg of Ferrous Ascorbate tablet per day and Group-B received 100mg of Ferric Pyrophosphate tablet per day. They were followed up every 30 days for 2 visits, to observe the improvement in the Haemoglobin (Hb) levels, Total iron binding capacity (Tibc), and serum ferritin, also any adverse drug reactions. We took an initiative to contact the participants every week so as to address any medication compliance issues. The data was secured and stored safely in Microsoft excel.

Statistical tools used:

Qualitative data was presented as number and percentage and Quantitative data was presented as mean and standard deviation. Statistical

significance between percentages was analysed using the t-test and Chi-square test. The complete analysis was done by using SPSS statistical package 26th version.

RESULTS

After 2nd review checkup, out of 98 patients recruited 15 were lost to follow-up between 1st and 2nd review visits. Group-A lost 6 participants while Group-B lost 9 participants. And finally, we assessed the results of 43 participants in Group-A and 40 in Group-B. The results presented below are the values that are checked before the start of the study Day - 0 and after the IDA therapy for about 2 months duration on Day-60. Laboratory test results for Hb, RBC's and Serum Ferritin for the Comparison of Group-A and Group-B are described below in (Table:1)

Hemoglobin:

Hb levels in Ferric Ascorbate group prior to the initiation of therapy on DAY-0 had 9.52 g/dL with

Mean standard deviation of (0.96) while after 2nd review of therapy DAY-60 was found to be 12.23 g/dL with Mean standard deviation of (1.39) which showed a significant change by 2.71g/dL whereas in Ferrous Pyrophosphate had 9.82g/dL during the initiation of therapy and later increased to 11.16g/dL.

Red blood cells count:

RBC'S count in Ferric Ascorbate group had 3.35 millions/cumm and later increased to 4.27 millions/cumm while in Ferrous Pyrophosphate group the value increased from 3.47 millions/cumm to 3.94 millions/cumm.

Serum Ferritin:

Ferrous Ascorbate group increased Serum Ferritin levels from 74.56 to 288.23 ng/mL and in Ferric Pyrophosphate the values increased from 82.63 ng/mL to 314.18 ng/mL.

Table1: Comparison Of Blood Tests for Group-A And Group-B

Variable	Ferrous Ascorbate		P value	Ferric Pyrophosphate		P value
	DAY-0 Mean (SD)	DAY-60 Mean (SD)		Day-0 Mean (SD)	DAY-60 Mean (SD)	
Hb	9.52 (0.96)	12.23 (1.39)	<0.001	9.82 (1.20)	11.16 (1.59)	<0.001
RBC count	3.35 (0.39)	4.27 (0.37)	<0.001	3.47 (0.42)	3.94 (0.37)	<0.001
Platelet count	2.76 (1.71)	3.48 (0.63)	0.003	2.12 (0.61)	2.54 (0.68)	<0.001
TIBC	488.44 (55.94)	421.26 (33.05)	<0.001	467.05 (40.69)	380.15 (62.16)	<0.001
Serum ferritin	74.56 (86.98)	288.23 (98.74)	<0.001	82.63 (79.92)	314.18 (52.42)	<0.001

The side effects such as nausea, vomiting, abdominal pain was reported in (Table: 2) for both the groups. Group-A had reported 6.97% and Group-B reported 2.5%.

Table2: Comparison of Side effects in Ferrous Ascorbate and Ferric Pyrophosphate

Side effects	Medication	
	Ferrous Ascorbate Number (%)	Ferric Pyrophosphate Number (%)

Yes	3 (6.97)	1 (2.5)
No	40 (93.03)	39 (97.5)
Total	43 (100)	40 (100)

The medication compliance or adherence was 88.38% in Ferrous Ascorbate group and Ferric Pyrophosphate group had 97.5% presented in (Table:3).

Table3: Medication compliance in Group-A and Group-B

Compliance	Medication	
	Ferrous Ascorbate Number (%)	Ferric Pyrophosphate Number (%)
Yes	38 (88.38)	39 (97.5)
No	5 (11.62)	1 (2.5)
Total	43 (100)	40 (100)

Medicine was discontinued in both the groups; 4 subjects in Group-A which is (9.30%) and 1 subject in Group-B which is (2.5%)

Table4: Comparison Of Medicine Discontinued in Both the Groups

Discontinue medication	Medication	
	Ferrous Ascorbate Number (%)	Ferric Pyrophosphate Number (%)
Yes	4 (9.30)	1 (2.5)
No	39 (90.70)	39 (97.5)
Total	43 (100)	40 (100)

DISCUSSION

Even though low-income nations are where IDA is most common. Prevalence of anemia during pregnancy is greater than 20% in more than 80% of the world's nations⁽¹²⁾. Most of this discrepancy can be attributed to the regular blood loss that occurs during menstruation, which is frequently linked to a low iron diet^(13,14). This study when compared Ferrous Ascorbate therapy with Ferric Pyrophosphate therapy found that there is a significant difference between both the groups. Ferrous Ascorbate showed better results in Hb levels by increase of 2.71g/dL while it increased

1.34g/dL in Ferric Pyrophosphate group. RBC count increased by 0.92millions/cumm in Group-A and 0.47millions/cumm in Group-B. Platelet count had a difference of 0.72Lakhs/Cumm in Ferrous Ascorbate while 0.42Lakhs/Cumm in Ferric Pyrophosphate group. Serum Ferritin levels had an increase of 213.67ng/mL in Group-A whereas 231.55ng/mL in Group-B. Tibc was found to be decreased in both the groups with more reduction in Ferric Pyrophosphate group. Coming to the side-effects compared in both the groups, 3 subjects from Ferrous Ascorbate group and only 1 person from Ferric Pyrophosphate complained about side-effects. Medication Compliance issues were reported in 5patients and out of which 4patients discontinued medicines in Ferrous Ascorbate group while 1person reported and discontinued medicine from Ferric Pyrophosphate group.

Characteristics of both the Medicines:

Ferrous Ascorbate -

- **Bioavailability:** Ferrous ascorbate is a combination of ferrous iron (Fe²⁺) and ascorbic acid (vitamin C). The ascorbic acid enhances the absorption of iron in the gastrointestinal tract, leading to higher bioavailability.
- **Efficacy:** It is generally considered effective in increasing hemoglobin levels and replenishing iron stores due to its high absorption rate.
- **Tolerability:** Some patients may experience gastrointestinal side effects such as nausea, constipation, and abdominal discomfort, which are common with ferrous iron supplements.

Ferric Pyrophosphate -

- **Bioavailability:** Ferric pyrophosphate contains ferric iron (Fe³⁺), which is less soluble and typically has lower bioavailability compared to ferrous iron. However, newer formulations and delivery methods (e.g., liposomal encapsulation) have been developed to enhance its absorption.
- **Efficacy:** It can be effective, especially in specific formulations designed to improve absorption. It is often used in fortification of foods and in patients with chronic kidney disease receiving dialysis.
- **Tolerability:** Ferric pyrophosphate is generally better tolerated than ferrous salts, with fewer gastrointestinal side effects.

CONCLUSION

- **For general use in treating iron deficiency anaemia:** Ferrous ascorbate is often preferred due to its higher bioavailability and efficacy. It is effective in increasing iron levels and improving anaemia.
- **For patients with gastrointestinal issues or poor tolerance to ferrous iron:** Ferric pyrophosphate can be a better alternative due to its better tolerability, though it may have lower bioavailability unless specially formulated.

This shows that though Ferrous Ascorbate therapy had better efficacy when compared with Ferric Pyrophosphate therapy, people felt better with Ferric Pyrophosphate. Ultimately, the choice between ferrous ascorbate and Ferric Pyrophosphate should be guided by individual patient needs, tolerability, and the specific clinical scenario.

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HOW TO CITE: Divya Sri, Keerthika B., Priyanka B., P. Harith, Mahesh Gomasa, Dr. Swathi Boddupally*, Study On Efficacy and Compliance of Oral Supplements with Ferric Pyrophosphate and Ferrous Ascorbate in Iron Deficiency Anaemia During Pregnancy. *J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, Vol 3, Issue 5, 1080-1086 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15354355>

